

**PROSPECTS OF THE USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN THE
ACTIVITIES OF THE INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES IN WORKING
WITH THE APPEALS OF INDIVIDUALS AND LEGAL ENTITIES**

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Annotation. In this article, the legal basis of the internal affairs bodies' work with appeals of individuals and legal entities, proposals for improving the use of modern information technologies in the work of internal affairs bodies with appeals, as a result of which the appeals of individuals and legal entities are considered in a timely manner and to prevent fraud opinions are held about its achievement.

Key words: individual, legal entity, application, complaint, proposal, technology, information, appeal.

An appeal is an action that a person communicates verbally, in writing, and electronically to another person or to state bodies in order to satisfy a material or non-material (especially legal assistance) need. People try to satisfy their various needs throughout their lives. One of them is the need to protect their rights and legal interests.

Specialists with sufficient knowledge, skills and experience in this field are needed to satisfy the need for protection of the rights and legal interests of individuals, as well as assistance in any legal matter (civil, administrative, criminal, labor, etc.). Today, in order to meet the needs of lawyers, a number of higher education institutions in our country, namely: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, Tashkent State Law University, University of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Nukus State University of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, University of World Economy and Diplomacy, a branch of Tashkent State Law

University and others higher education institutions have been preparing such legal specialists for practice.

It's no secret that citizens first of all turn to the employees of the internal affairs bodies (mainly the district prevention inspector) asking for the protection of their violated rights and legal interests, as well as the realization of their legal rights. Because every person (individual and legal entity) sees in the image of an employee of internal affairs bodies a person who protects the rights and legal interests of individuals, who is well versed in jurisprudence. From this point of view, it is no exaggeration to say that district prevention inspectors, who are the lowest level of internal affairs bodies, deal with appeals first and consider appeals.

In this regard, the employees of the internal affairs bodies are required to know well every branch of the legal field and to assist citizens in considering their appeals. After all, the main tasks of internal affairs bodies are to protect the rights, freedoms and legal interests of citizens, the property of physical and legal entities, the constitutional system, to ensure the rule of law, the safety of individuals, society and the state, as well as to prevent and prevent crimes.

In his solemn speech dedicated to the 27th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Honorable President of the Republic of Uzbekistan made a special mention of the work of law enforcement agencies with the appeals of individuals and legal entities, saying "...most of the appeals coming to the People's reception desks are related to shortcomings in the work of the court, prosecutor's office, and internal affairs agencies. Taking this into account, it is necessary for these agencies to create a completely new system of working with our people. The legal solution to every application and complaint will be the evaluation of the activities of the heads of these departments.

Based on this, it can be said that there are a lot of normative documents that regulate the work of internal affairs bodies with the appeals of individuals and legal entities, and according to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Normative-

Legal Documents", based on the priority levels of normative legal documents, they are the following can be divided into four main classifications.

- Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
- Decrees, orders and decisions issued by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
- Normative legal documents of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
- Departmental regulatory documents regulating the activities of the internal affairs bodies for considering the appeals of individuals and legal entities

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 7, 2017 "On Dissemination of Legal Information and Ensuring its Use". The purpose of this Law is to regulate relations in the field of distribution of legal information and provision of its use.

Legal information means the texts of regulatory legal documents, official comments on them, explanations on the procedure for the application of regulatory legal documents, decisions of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the application of legal documents, as well as materials summarizing judicial practice. The use of legal information is guaranteed by the state. Citizens have the right to freely seek, receive and disseminate legal information.

State bodies, other organizations and officials must provide everyone with access to legal information in the prescribed manner.

The methods of disseminating legal information are as follows:

- sending texts of regulatory legal documents;
- official publication of regulatory legal documents;
- unofficial publication of normative legal documents;
- implementation of legal advocacy;

providing legal information to individuals and legal entities upon their request.

At this point, we consider it appropriate to introduce legal information channels in social networks of each state body in order to widely introduce the distribution of legal information. Today, social networks have become an integral part of the lives of individuals. It would not be an exaggeration to say that social networks have become faster than mass media. It's no secret that even mass media are publishing articles based on information spread on social networks. Therefore, we think that it is necessary to accept the appeals sent to state bodies through social networks and to register and consider them in the appropriate order (of course, identifying the identity of the applicant). There are many examples of social media referrals. For example, former internal affairs officer S. Otaboev's speech on social networks, appeals of the former Bukhara city prosecutor, who addressed the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan through "Youtube", which is considered a social network and a global Internet network, are among these.

Individuals and legal entities have the right to apply to state bodies and organizations with a request to provide legal information related to their activities. The request for the provision of legal information should be considered within fifteen days from the date of its receipt.

Providing legal information electronically is free of charge. A fee may be charged for the provision of legal information in paper form upon agreement of the parties. Refusal to satisfy a request for the provision of legal information must be justified.

As another practical example of the distribution of legal information, it is possible to cite the fact that the head of the IIB of Pakhtaabad district of Andijan region organized a separate group for receiving appeals on the Telegram social network, many citizens sent their appeals to this group, received reasonable legal answers, and submitted their appeals in time through the relevant state bodies. it can

be seen that he has reached a solution and sent thanks to the head of the Pakhtaabad district IIB. In our opinion, it is appropriate to introduce this experience in other places of the republic.

In conclusion, it can be said that the activities of the internal affairs bodies related to consideration of appeals of individuals and legal entities are comprehensively regulated on the basis of a number of laws and regulations and departmental normative legal documents. Therefore, it is necessary to study the legal bases regulating the activity in this area with a comprehensive approach.

References:

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